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STUDY OF MIXED-LIGAND CHROME COMPLEX BASED ON QINALDILIC ACID AND SEMICARBAZIDE

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Annotation: Conditions have been established for the synthesis of a mixed-ligand chromium complex composed of quinaldic acid and coordinated water molecules. The ensuing complex compounds were analyzed using elemental analysis, X-ray diffraction, IR and UV spectroscopy.

Key words: quinaldic acid, chromium, crystal structure, biological ligand.

Coordination complexes of metals with biologically active ligands possess diverse properties and can find applications in several scientific disciplines. Quinaldic acid is one such ligand. Its reaction with divalent or trivalent metals creates five-membered rings resulting from the quinaldate anion's ligation [1-5]. The ortho position pyridine ring and carboxylate group within quinaldic acid function as a donor set [6]. Studies have demonstrated that quinaldic acid can coordinate as a monodentate or bidentate ligand; however, it rarely exhibits a bridging function [7-11].

Semicarbazide, a nitrogen-containing ligand, possesses remarkable chelating properties and can form robust metal complexes.

This research investigates the specific aspects of the coordination of chromium with quinaldic acid and semicarbazide. A novel chromium coordination compound $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ was produced through research with a yield of up to 72%. Synthesising underwent with a ratio of 1:1:1 at a temperature of 40°C and at an aqueous solution pH of 4.5 - 7.0. X-ray diffraction analysis, elemental analysis, IR spectroscopy, and UV spectroscopy were used to verify the structure and composition of the synthesised compound. The $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ complex forms a monoclinic unit cell with a chiral space group. The coordination number of this compound is 6. The chromium atom at the center is linked to quinaldic acid via N,O coordination, resulting in an octahedral coordination (Fig. 1, 2).

Fig.1. Molecular structure of $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ with atomic numbering scheme.

The composition of the isolated compounds was analysed through elemental analysis (refer to Table 1) and IR spectroscopy. The IR spectra of the complex and the starting substances, namely semicarbazide, quinaldic acid and chromium nitrate, demonstrated changes in the frequencies of the IR spectrum during the formation of the complex. Additionally, the presence of frequencies corresponding to the stretching vibrations of the NH of the $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ complex, which were detected in the characteristic quinaldic acid $\nu(NH)$ spectral lines, were recognized (refer to Fig. 3).

Fig.2. View of the $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ packing along the b axis of the unit cell.

The presence of M-O and M-N bond vibrations was not identified in the ligands, confirming the compound as a metal complex. The IR spectra analysis revealed the existence of functional groups of quinaldic acid in the regions of 1631 cm^{-1} and 1592 cm^{-1} , with quinaldine ring vibrations also observed in the complex's IR spectra. The findings are consistent with the X-ray structures provided earlier for the complexes.

Figure 3. IR spectra of the $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ complex.

In the UV spectra of the complex, spectra resembling those of the ligand with a significant shoulder at 318 nm are detected. Nevertheless, dissimilarity in absorption intensity is evident in the complex's spectra, showing a marked hyperchromic effect.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data for the $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ metal complex.

Compound	Color	$\mu S/cm$	Elemental analysis (%) calcd. (found)		
			C	H	N
$C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$	Brown	81	49.61 (49.59)	3.30 (3.28)	5.78 (5.75)

A procedure has been devised for synthesising the coordination compound $C_{10}H_8NO_3Cr$ with quinaldic acid in a 1:1:1 ratio. The composition, uniqueness, and several physicochemical characteristics of the extracted complex have been determined. It has been found, through conducted investigations, that quinaldic acid chelates the metal atom through its heterocyclic nitrogen atom and the oxygen atom of the carboxyl group within the complex. The resulting complex with possible biological activity is of interest for further study of its properties in the field of application as a liquid fertilizer.

REFERENCES:

1. A. Vogel, A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis, 3rd edn. Longman, London (1962).
2. R. A. K. Majumdar and J. O. Gupta, Z. Anal. Chem. 1958,161, 100.
3. R. A. K. Majumdar and J. O. Gupta, Z. Anal. Chem. 1958,161, 181.
4. R. A. K. Majumdar and J. P. Bag, Anal. Chim. Acta 1960, 22, 549.
5. B. W. Banerjee and J. P. Ray, Znd. Chem. Sot. 1958, 35, 299.
6. Geiger, O.; Gorisch, H. " Biochem. J. 1989, 261, 415–421.
7. N. Okabe, Y.i. Muranishi, Acta Cryst. C 59 (2003) m228–m230.
8. M. Cano, J.V. Heras, M.A. Lobo, E. Pinilla, M.A. Monge, Polyhedron 13 (1994) 1563–1573.
9. D. Dobrzynska, M. Duczmal, L.B. Jerzykiewicz, J. Warchulska, K. Drabent, Eur. J. Inorg. Chem. 2004 (2004) 110–117.
10. S.L. Jain, A.M.Z. Slawin, J.D. Woollins, P. Bhattacharyya, Eur. J. Inorg. Chem. 2005 (2005) 721–726.
11. E.J. Gabe, F.L. Lee, L.E. Khoo, F.E. Smith, Inorg. Chim. Acta 105 (1985) 103–106.

**«ХИМИЯ ЖӘНЕ ҚОРШАҒАН ОРТА» ТАҚЫРЫБЫНА ТАНЫМДЫҚ ЕСЕПТЕР
ШЫҒАРУ МҮМКІНШІЛІКТЕРІ**

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«Химия және қоршаған орта» тақырыбына танымдық есептер шығару мүмкіншіліктері

Химия пәнінен оқушылардың көп қиналатыны химиялық есептер. Түрлі тақырыптарға берілетін есептеулерге оқушылардың қызығуын тудыру үшін олардың теориялық жағын сабақ мазмұнымен байланыстыра түсіндірген көп нәтиже береді. Сандай –ақ сабақта оқушыларға берілген есептермен қатар химияның күнделікті тұрмыстағы, қоршаған ортада қолданылуына байланысты есептер оқушының қызығуын тудырып, танымдық көзқарасын кеңейтеді. Сондықтан химияның қарапайым тақырыптарына арналған есептердің азғантай теориялық мазмұны мен оларға танымдық есептер ұсынып отырмын.

Есептердің таным процесіндегі ролі өте зор. Есеп шығару кезінде оқушылардың ойлау қабілеттері тез дамиды. Сондықтан орта мектепте математика, физика, химия пәндерін оқыту кезінде сандық және сапалық есептер шығару өте маңызды орыналады.

ТАЈІЕВА ГАЛІЯ РУСЛАНОВНА (TASHKENT, UZBEKISTAN) STUDY OF MIXED-LIGAND CHROME COMPLEX BASED ON QINALDILIC ACID AND SEMICARBAZIDE.....	67
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